

COMPETENCY MODEL FOR CONSTRUCTION FIELD STUDENTS BASED ON MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *This article examines the development of a competency model based on modern educational technologies for students in the construction field. It analyzes the theoretical foundations and practical significance of the competency-based approach, the application of integrative-technological tasks in the educational process, as well as new directions of professional training in the digital economy. The article emphasizes that through the implementation of interactive methods and information-communication technologies in the educational process, it is possible to develop students' practical skills and form abilities for independent thinking and professional decision-making. This model is presented as an effective tool for training modern specialists in the construction field.*

Keywords: *competency model, modern educational technologies, construction field, professional education, integrative-technological tasks, digital economy, information-communication technologies, practical skills, educational effectiveness.*

Introduction. The competency-based approach plays an important role in the modern education system as it prepares students not only with theoretical knowledge but also for its application in practical activities. Especially in technical fields such as construction, this approach significantly improves the quality of personnel training. To prepare specialists who can meet labor market demands, think independently, and solve complex problems, it is necessary to enrich the educational process with modern educational technologies. This article is dedicated to studying the theoretical foundations of the competency model and its practical significance for students in the construction field. Research conducted by N.E.Erganova and G.R.Muginova highlights the possibilities of integrative-technological tasks in implementing a competency-based approach in professional education. In this scientific work, organizing the educational process based on integrated technologies is considered an important factor in forming competencies. As the authors emphasize, the formation of practical skills along with theoretical knowledge in students can be effectively implemented through an integrative approach.[1] The research results substantiate that professional competency can be developed by introducing a comprehensive approach to the teaching process. This approach is practically useful in enhancing the professional training of construction field students through the application of modern educational technologies. Integrative-technological tasks serve the systematic formation of educational content and the development of the student's personality. These aspects can be considered as the main theoretical foundation in developing the competency model.

In an article published in 2007 in the journal "Educational Technologies and Society," G.I. Ibragimov extensively covers the theoretical foundations and practical significance of the competency-based approach in professional education. The author interprets the concept of competency not just as a set of knowledge and skills but as a system of complex qualities necessary for successful work in professional activities.[2] This approach shows that the

teacher's task is not to deliver ready-made knowledge but to develop students' professional competencies through organizing their practice-oriented independent activities. Ibragimov emphasizes that implementing a competency-based approach in professional education requires a fundamental renewal of the curriculum content. The use of modern educational technologies plays an important role in this process because pedagogical innovations ensure that students acquire knowledge based on their proximity to the real professional environment by creating activating forms of teaching. These ideas can serve as the main methodological direction in developing a competency model for construction field students. In such a model, theoretical knowledge should be directed toward forming the student's potential for independent and responsible professional decision-making through practical tasks, problem-solving assignments, and collaborative projects.

Research conducted by N.E.Erganova and G.R.Muginova scientifically highlights the potential of integrative-technological tasks in implementing a competency-based approach in professional education. The authors emphasize that by using integrated tasks, it is possible to ensure the harmonization of theoretical knowledge and practical skills. Such an approach is considered effective in preparing students to solve real professional problems. The application of integrative-technological tasks in the competency model being developed for construction field students ensures their acquisition of interdisciplinary knowledge and forms abilities for independent professional thinking. In G.I.Ibragimov's research on the competency-based approach in professional education, the concept of competency is deeply analyzed. The author indicates this concept not just as a sum of knowledge and skills but as a system of complex qualities necessary for successful work in professional activities. It is noted that the main task of a teacher is to organize students' practice-oriented independent activities. If the competency model in the construction field is formed on this methodological basis, adaptability to the real professional environment, responsibility, and creative approach will develop in students.

The scientific article by K.I.Makaeva and co-authors on the essence of risks and uncertainties in the management field provides a deep analysis of the theoretical and practical aspects of risk factors. Identifying and effectively dealing with risks that arise in the decision-making process is interpreted as an important aspect of manager competency.[3] In the competency model being developed for construction field students, interdisciplinary knowledge related to risks is of great importance, and the formation of these skills is carried out through modern educational technologies. Through this approach, students develop abilities for analytical thinking, responsible decision-making, and action in complex situations.

In the article "Methods of Forming Core Competencies Based on Digital Economy for Future Construction Technicians" published in 2021 in the journal "Innovative Development Professional Education" by T. Krashakova and I.I. Tuber, methods of forming core competencies for future construction technicians in the digital economy are extensively analyzed. The authors demonstrate ways to develop students' knowledge and skills through integrating modern educational technologies into the learning process.[4] They pay special attention to developing technical and information-communication potentials that meet the requirements of the digital economy. This approach is important in preparing construction field specialists for the modern work environment. The article examines possibilities for increasing the effectiveness of forming competencies through the application of innovative methods in the educational process. This research is an important scientific source in developing a competency model based on modern educational technologies for construction field students. Through the implementation of modern educational technologies, the learning process is organized with the student's activity at the

center. Through interactive methods such as project-based learning, problem-based teaching, situational analyses, simulation and experience-based exercises, and approaches focused on practical tasks, the student's knowledge deepens. In the construction field, through these methods, students acquire competencies in design, engineering analysis, working with regulatory documents, selecting modern technological solutions, and applying them in practice.

The application of information-communication technologies in the educational process serves to improve the quality of education. Through virtual laboratories, constructor programs, automated design tools, BIM (Building Information Modeling) systems, students reinforce their theoretical knowledge based on real objects. With such technologies, students can visually analyze real problems, correctly prepare technical documents, and develop skills in managing the construction process based on a multidisciplinary approach. This brings their professional training closer to practical work conditions. Assessment criteria are also important in organizing education based on the competency model. Instead of the traditional rating system, methods such as formative and summative assessment, portfolio maintenance, self-assessment, and peer assessment allow for consistent monitoring of the student's personal and professional growth. This evaluates not only knowledge but also universal competencies such as communication culture, teamwork skills, critical thinking, initiative, leadership, and stress resistance.

As labor market demands change, updating, modularizing, and individualizing curricula are becoming necessary for preparing suitable personnel for the construction field. Developing an appropriate educational trajectory based on each student's personal needs, knowledge level, and professional direction is considered an approach characteristic of the competency model. Through this, students become deeply specialized professionals according to their interests. For example, some might strive to become experts in construction technology, while others might specialize in budget estimation, technical supervision, or project management. Forming communicative and information literacy is also one of the important directions for students in the construction engineering field. The ability to study new modern construction technologies requires understanding international standards, foreign languages, and analyzing technical documents. This necessitates mastering English at the level of technical terminology, understanding technical drawings and project documents, and effectively collaborating with international project teams. By forming technical and legal literacy in students, they become prepared to independently perform tasks such as drafting contracts, reading technical indicators, and controlling quality standards.

In the education system based on the competency model for the construction field, specific competencies are also formed regarding engineering ethics, environmental responsibility, and adherence to health and safety standards. Taking into account the principles of sustainable development, students develop awareness and practical skills in selecting environmentally sustainable materials, energy-efficient design, and minimizing negative impacts on the environment. This serves to prepare specialists who can meet modern global requirements. Developing innovative competencies increases the openness to technological innovations and competitiveness of students in the construction field. Readiness to master new construction materials, robotics, artificial intelligence, and automated construction systems allows them not only to efficiently implement existing projects but also to offer new solutions. In an educational environment based on the competency approach, the ability to search for, analyze, and implement such innovations plays an important role. Specialists prepared based on the competency model for the construction field become not only dedicated to their profession but also individuals who feel social responsibility, are capable of teamwork, tolerant of cultural

differences, and constantly strive for self-development. This increases their potential to work on a global scale and provides advantages in the national labor market. Through the content, methods, and tools of education formed on the basis of the competency model, the comprehensive development of students is ensured.

Conclusion: The competency model developed for construction field students should be provided with extensive application of modern educational technologies. Through integrative-technological tasks and interactive methods, students can acquire practical skills and develop abilities for independent and responsible professional decision-making. Forming technical and information-communication potentials that meet the requirements of the digital economy increases the effectiveness of the educational process. The competency model plays an important role in preparing for modern professions by providing an educational trajectory adapted to the individual needs and interests of the student. At the same time, the renewal of the assessment system allows for continuous monitoring of the student's personal and professional development. As a result, the competency-based approach emerges as an effective method for preparing modern, competitive specialists for the construction field.

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